

Water cortisol is a reliable indicator of stress in European sea bass, *Dicentrarchus labrax*

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Summary

This study examined cortisol release into the water by European sea bass, *Dicentrarchus labrax*. The time-course of plasma and water cortisol concentrations were determined in adult fish subjected to acute stress, by sampling blood and water at 0 h (before stress) and 0.5, 1, 2, 4, 8 and 24 h after stress. Sea bass showed a typical stress response, with plasma glucose and lactate concentrations peaking at 2 h, and plasma cortisol levels peaking at 1 h. Cortisol release rate into the water increased in response to stress and was positively correlated with plasma cortisol concentrations. In a further trial, juvenile fish were confined at densities of 20 and 50 kg/m³ and water cortisol was evaluated over a 24 h period. Cortisol release rates peaked between 0–1 h in the high and 1–2 h in the low density group. In conclusion, these results provide strong evidence that cortisol release rate into the water can be used as a non-invasive method for the assessment of the stress response and that although sea bass presents a high blood stress response after exposure to acute husbandry stressors, it is releasing less cortisol into the water compared to other species previously examined.